

Superpower Nation-States have gone Rogue: Where is the Accountability?

Ronald Turner

I6425811

Maastricht University

11 June 2026

Author Note

This paper was prepared for M.Sc. Public Policy and Human Development (2025-2026)

Khalid Koser (Thesis Supervisor)

Abstract

Since the beginning of George W. Bush's presidency in 2001, countries such as the United States, Russia, and China have shown an ever-increasing open hostility to their collective defense allies in the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), their global trading partners, and to the international community. These hostilities have evolved into contempt for the United Nations (UN) and its members whose mandate is international Peace & Security. These same nation-states consistently demonstrate unreserved trade and economic bullying toward their European Union (EU) Canadian, United Kingdom, and Asian-Pacific trade members. Here in the beginning of the second quarter of the 21st Century (2026), open hostility, contempt, trade and economic bullying can be seen on global news stations in real time. These news presenters consistently report on the negative comments regarding international organizations made by Donald Trump, who is currently the U.S. elected leader. This reporting and the meticulous documentation by international organizations over time has shown that from 2001 until present day the U.S. government along with countries such as the Russian Federation led by Vladimir Putin, have engaged in words and deeds against the international community in a Rogue-like manner. This behavior has currently put the world into a severe state of chaos that is, reflected by increased wars, conflict, forced migration, and ever-increasing trade and economic instability. The Geopolitical scales are at a tipping point with China and Russia already being governed by authoritarian leaders, the United States having been a Democratic Republic for 241 years, now leaning in the direction of authoritarianism under the Presidency of Donald J. Trump. Countries like China, Russia, and the United States with their Rogue-like behavior are inflicting enormous harm on the global community without being held accountable for their egregious actions. This study utilizes qualitative methods and case studies to explore accountability and enforcement shortcomings of international laws, policies, and treaties and

innovative ideas that will address the resulting rogue-like behavior of some of the international players.

Introduction

On January 2026, the President of the United States Donald J. Trump authorized military action against Venezuela. The world woke to the breaking news that the American government without international approval or justifiable provocation invaded the sovereign country of Venezuela. American military weapons, along with military personnel on the ground caused destruction to the city of Caracas and kidnapped Venezuelan President Nicholas Maduro and his wife. Donald Trump initially stated that his reason for this action was National Security and later claimed that President Maduro was part of a drug organization shipping large amounts of illegal drugs into the United States of America. Mr. Trump has failed to present any evidence to support his claims. As of September 2025, under the authorization of Mr. Trump the U. S. military has conducted numerous lethal strikes on small civilian boats operating in or near Venezuelan waters. Mr. Trump's authorization was again a unilateral decision without approval from Congress nor in consultation with international allies. Mr. Trump has again failed to present justification or evidence for the destruction of alleged drug boats and the killing of those on board the vessels. To date at least 25 operations have been conducted, resulting in at least 95 deaths.

This action would be understandable if the government of Venezuela had declared war on or attacked the United States. Mr. Trump, and his administration, with the approval of Congress, the American people, and international support would have been justified in retaliating. But the most recent actions of Mr. Trump and his administration and their failure to provide any evidence to Congress, the American people, or to their international allies'

calls into question these actions. The complete disregard for the international community and international law must also be considered.

Mr. Trump's unilateral decisions, against Venezuela, and a growing number of other countries around the world, fall into a category of what is known as rogue like behavior and/or a rogue state with regards to the United States as a nation. A rogue state as defined by the Collins English Dictionary in British English (2026) as, "a state that conducts its policy in a dangerously unpredictable way, disregarding international law or diplomacy." By no means is Mr. Trump and his administration the first in American history to travel down the path of rogue like behavior. There are many other past United States presidents, such as Kennedy, Johnson, and Nixon; all of which were deeply involved in the Vietnam War. This war was a reprehensible violation of international law, covered a 14-year span and involved the three forementioned President's and their administrations staff. Author, Carl Boggs (2010) wrote of Christopher Eric Hitchens, once a British American author and journalist as having identified Henry Kissinger, the U S National Security Advisor and Secretary of State at the time "as a mass murderer and a war criminal for his role in Indochina" (p. 30). Again, the United States is not alone, other less powerful government leaders and countries around the world are walking the same path. This study will examine the matter of rogue-like behavior through the lens of three key questions:

1. *What are the accountability mechanisms currently at the international community's disposal?*
2. *What is the evidence that the international system for accountability is no longer effective?*
3. *What are the options for strengthening accountability by the international community?*

International laws, treaties, and policies have failed to hold Rogue States accountable. Democratic governments are on the decline as dictatorships and authoritarian governments are on the rise. There is an immediate call to action to rethink current international systems, laws, treaties and policies. To consider new and innovative ways to hold Rogue States accountable for the chaos, death, and destruction they bring to the world. After all, without accountability and enforcement; chaos, death, and destruction will remain the norm in our international relations.

Literature and Theory

To understand the path international governance can take to successfully transition into a more productive future, we need to explore the past and what it reveals of the Rogue States, their evolution, and the failure of accountability and enforcement within the international system, international laws, and policies.

Payne (2016) informs us that in 1648 at the end of the “Thirty Years’ War” a notable settlement known as the “*Peace of Westphalia*” had been adopted. This came about subsequent to a destructive period of war that resulted in the death of millions. One of the most notable issues addressed was *state autonomy* or Westphalian sovereignty, which was the idea that states have authority over their own territory and domestic affairs. This is important because the Westphalian Conference set the precedence for multilateral diplomatic matters and shaped the foundation of modern state systems (p. 2).

Hundreds of years after the ‘Thirty Years War’ many organizations have since emerged mostly during the mid-1940s. Organizations such as the League of Nations was born and would quickly become known as the United Nations (U.N.), the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank (WB), and the General Agreement on Tariffs & Trade (GATT) later to be known as the World Trade Organization (WTO) all grew from this period. As

country lines on a map were being redrawn, along with the reconstruction of Europe, and the re-establishment of the European economy, leaders of the free world decided that they would try economics and trade as a mechanism to ward off any desire to start World War III. This mechanism has worked for many years in the prevention of World War III; and has led to the establishment of the current global economy. But economics and trade have not stopped the continued build-up of military equipment, personnel, as well as the continuous wars and conflicts around the planet. The three Superpower countries, China, Russia, and the United States have budgeted enormous amounts of money into their militaries. The following numbers were reported for fiscal year 2024 in the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute's fact sheet dated 2025.

Country	Most Recent Military Budget	Source
China	\$314 Billion (2024, estimated)	SIPRI
Russia	\$149 Billion (2024, estimated)	SIPRI
United States	\$997 Billion (2024)	SIPRI

Sources: SIPRI Military Expenditure Database, Apr. 2025; International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, Oct. 2024; and International Monetary Fund, International Financial Statistics Database, Sep. 2024.

These three countries together account for a dominant share of global military spending. This outsized spending generated a higher concentration of might and power. These same three countries are members of the U.N.'s primary five countries which have veto powers among the 193 UN membership. Boggs (2010), in chapter 5, of 'A Tale of Broken Treaties' writes of decades of documented violations and circumvented treaties which the U.S. government had thought to be impediments to American national goals. This veto power also concentrated a significant amount of dominance into the hands of these five countries.

The accountability mechanisms that are currently in place are many and bring into alignment many of the worlds economically, and military small and medium nation states. Unfortunately, with Superpower nation states the international community has not found a

way to realign and/or hold Superpower nation states accountability for their rogue behavior. Over time the current international legal mechanisms, (i.e. courts, tribunals, and treaty bodies, etc.) reveal their limitations. First the Courts, Tribunals, and Treaty Bodies. Within the body of the United Nations, which consists of six subgroups, one of those subgroups is known as the International Court of Justice (ICJ). The ICJ is the primary judicial part of the UN with the mandate to settle legal disputes between Nation States and provide advisory opinions. Professor Wolfgang G. Friedmann once a German American legal scholar who specialized in international law gave a glimpse of the ICJ and its evolutionary journey since 1945 in his 1970 essay, *'The International Court of Justice and the Evolution of International Law'*. In it he wrote of the scarcity of using the ICJ in cases in which there was high political drama. "We will have to accept that in the present state of international society the International Court will seldom be called upon and is generally unable to solve disputes of vital political significance" (p. 320). Friedmann (1970), writes about societal limitations within the jurisdiction of the ICJ and that the court reflects the state of society in which it operates. "It cannot move too far ahead of the deeply divided nationalistic and ideologically split world in which it operates." (p. 320) This concept is as true today as it was in 1970. Friedmann expounds on one of the major contributions of the ICJ to the structure of international organizations, and its ability to provide Advisory Opinion at the request of the United Nations. He gives one of three examples: The Bernadotte Opinion, the court firmly stood by "the international legal status of the United Nations as an entity empowered to act on behalf of its servants and to bring international claims against any state or other international entity" (p. 314). Furthermore, Friedmann worried about bias among the judgeship, he wrote on a case concerning South African apartheid and the reversal of a previous decision in which a blow was struck to the South African apartheid system. In this case one American judge, Judge Jessup "was the only national of a Western country among the dissenters, while the

Australian president (casting a double vote) and the British, French, and Italian judges formed part of the majority, strengthened the widely held opinion that the Court is weighted in favor of * colonialism*. What matters is not whether this view is justified, but whether it is held” (p. 313). In other words, can the opinion of colonial bias by members of the judgeship be a determining factor in the reversal of the court’s decision on this case?

The International Criminal Court (ICC) mandate is considerably different than that of the International Court of Justice (ICJ). The ICCs mandate is very specific and deliberately narrow. Which is to investigate and prosecute individuals, not Nation States for gravest international crimes when national justice systems fail or refuse to act. The main mandate for the ICC is *Article 5* of the *Rome Statute*. The ICC can only prosecute under four categories: Genocide, Crimes against Humanity, War Crimes, and Crime of Aggression.

The theory of Conditional Impact and Accountability Mechanisms of the ICC can be brought to light in such articles as Jo and Simmons (2016) article, ‘Can the International Criminal Court Deter Atrocity?’ The authors make the point that some criminal justice specialists believe “that the ICC does not have the resources to make punishment a real risk” (p.446). But the authors believe the mere jurisdictional reach of the ICC “increases the risk of prosecution compared with impunity” (p. 446). Leading to the deterrence of some individuals from committing such crimes under which the ICC can prosecute. The ICC’s legal authority can be seen to have a conditional impact through two forms of deterrence. Prosecutorial Deterrence and Social Deterrence. “Prosecutorial Deterrence refers to the omission of a criminal act out of fear of sanctions resulting from legal prosecution” (p. 446). Social Deterrence refers to the theory that individuals are discouraged from engaging in deviant or criminal behavior due to the fear of punishment or negative consequences. At some point the idea of Prosecutorial Deterrence leaned toward the concept of if the punishment was more severe than the crime it would keep individuals from committing unlawful acts. Jo and

Simmons (2016) wrote, “this fueled the move toward harsher sentencing in the United States in the 1980s” (p. 447). For developing countries, as on the continent of Africa, Jo and Simmons (2016) reported, “A large study affiliated with the World Bank based on developing countries found that higher conviction rates tended to reduce crime...Major texts on criminal deterrence in Africa agree that the key to crime control in most contexts in Africa is not the severity of punishment, but its likelihood” (p. 447). Such tactics work in developing countries but Superpower Rogue Nation States which violate international law; simply state to the international community that ‘it is better to ask for your forgiveness than to get your permission’.

In sum, Jo and Simmons (2016) concluded, “ICC investigations, indictments, and convictions or those triggered by Nation State trials, or court reforms which make trials more probable and credible are likely to encourage actual or potential perpetrators to reassess the risks of punishment—relative to the status quo, which is often impunity—and to moderate their behavior. Unfortunately, these hopes do not have the same effect on the leaders of the United States, the Russian Federation, nor The People’s Republic of China. Impunity is a shield these countries wear proudly. As for Social Deterrence, Jo and Simmons (2016) quote Zimring and Hawkins by noting Social Deterrence or, “the extralegal consequences from conviction appear to be at least as great a deterrent as the legal consequences” (p. 450). Jo and Simmons (2016) make the point that, “As the world’s first permanent and global criminal court, the ICC is especially central in defining international society’s response to international crimes” (p. 451). With the ICC’s ability to define international society’s response to international crimes and with further support via Social Deterrence the expectations of prosecutions can only rise while raising social expectations regarding what constitutes justice.

In addition to the courts within the International legal framework of international accountability, Tribunals have their own makeup of legal mechanisms. Tribunals use a very

different set of accountability mechanisms. Tribunals are specialized bodies that settle disputes in specific areas of the law. In the performance of their duties, which are like courts but basically faster, more accessible, and less formal. The most heard of Tribunals in recent history are the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY) and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR). Meron (2005), article “Judicial Independence and Impartiality in International Criminal Tribunals” writes about several key mechanisms used during the prosecution of Tribunals (p. 359). The author sets the mood for the discussion, by reminding readers about the role of Judicial Independence. The author holds Judicial Independence as a high priority for the rule of law. In today's world where countries such as the United States use thuggish and bullish coercion to interfere with Judicial Independence and Prosecutorial duties of the courts in the pursuit of accountability are becoming the new normal. Meron (2005) writes, “the ability to resolve disputes fairly is also essential to a stable economy and polity. The economic and political actors need to believe that an impartial arbiter will adjudicate their differences, and that their reliance on the existing laws and regulations will be honored” (p. 359). He also views judicial independence in the light of independent courts with the ability to hold governments accountable under their nation's laws. For the survival of Judicial Independence Meron (2005) believes that “the institution must have a variety of internal mechanism either to filter out potential bias or to correct it before the result becomes final” (p. 361). The first mechanism is ‘multijudge panels. All trials have at least three judges on the trial bench and five judges on the appeals bench. This structure prevents any one judicial member who may be biased from affecting the outcome of the trial. The second mechanism is what is known as the appellate review. Meron (2005), states that “Appellate review seeks to ensure that decisions of lower courts are accurate and uniform, and that injustice is not committed” (p. 361). The last mechanism

available to Tribunals is known as ‘Internal Committees and Guidelines’. These are mechanisms which ensure compliance with judicial ethics.

Prior to the writing of Meron’s (2005) 11-page editorial comment paper the ICTY and the ICTR paved the way for the ICC, additional conceptual frameworks and additional mechanisms which have assisted in moving international law further down the road. The International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR) were established by the United Nations (UN) Security Council to prosecute individuals who were responsible for mass atrocities in the Yugoslav Wars (ICTY) and the Rwandan Genocide (ICTR). Their establishment would usher in the modern international criminal legal system, individual accountability, and as mentioned earlier would later create the International Criminal Court (ICC). ICTY was created under UN Security Council Resolution 827 in 1993. It operated from 1993 – 2017. The ICTY was the first war crimes tribunal since the Nuremburg and Tokyo tribunals. The ICTY prosecuted individuals for genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. It also established that senior leaders can be held individually accountable, regardless of political or military ranking. At the same time creating historical records of the atrocities.

In the case of the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR), it was created under UN Security Council Resolution 955 in 1994 to prosecute those responsible for the 1994 Rwandan Genocide, in which approximately 800,000 Tutsi and Hutu African peoples were killed. This tribunal was in operation from 1994 – 2015. The ICTR was the first tribunal to deliver a genocide conviction for a head of government (Jean Kambanda) who was a former Rwandan Prime Minister serving in 1994. This tribunal also pioneered jurisprudence/the theory of law regarding rape as an act of genocide. Thanks to this Tribunal there has been a development of legal definitions, and standards for genocide as well as providing a model for hybrid and domestic accountability mechanisms within Africa.

Tribunals are just one of several mechanisms which are available to the international community. Others would include the Media and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs). In the last twenty years there has been an increased focus and participation of Media and Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in pushing back in the arena of Fake-News and helping the established journalistic and media outlets to provide accurate information locally, regionally, nationally, and globally. Fengler, Eberwein, and Karmasin (2021) suggested that “existing research showed that CSOs help preserve democracy” (p.85). Free press is one of the avenues for monitoring and disseminating information about governments. CSOs also create platforms whereby citizens can interact, the organizations can build trust and share information. CSOs use their networks and finances to bring important information to voters, the public masses, and fellow international CSOs. Unfortunately, the kryptonite to CSOs successes in helping to preserve democracy are the restrictions put in place by authoritarian and authoritarian-like governments. The restrictions reduce CSOs abilities to monitor, inform, to network, and mobilize. Fengler et al. (2021) provides the following example of such government restrictions, “As with the case of Turkey demonstrates, repression of the right to protest was pre-emptively used in 2017 to de-mobilize civil society before an anti-democratic constitutional referendum that removed horizontal accountability on executive powers” (p. 86). Horizontal Accountability refers to one of the mechanisms by which different branches or agencies of government as well as non-governmental agencies hold each other accountable, ensuring that no one branch of government operates without oversight. This form of accountability prevents abuse of power, promotes transparency, and helps to improve governance. Protections of CSOs are required to not only give support to civil societies, but also to prevent the backsliding of horizontal accountability of government institutions. Consequently, Fengler et al. (2021) wrote, “Restrictions on CSO activity are not the only authoritarian tool that may facilitate democratic erosion. Future research should

systematically investigate the institutional consequences of other government strategies to avoid accountability, i.e. the killing of journalists, interference in academic organizations, and restrictions on Internet freedom” (p. 105).

Dr. Karen Alter (2013) sees a silver lining for international court (IC) institutions and for international law through the veil of what she calls, “the new international judicial architecture” (p. 3). Alter (2013) leads with, “International relations have long been considered outside of the domain of law. Most people presume that law is only meaningful when backed by a central enforcer. By this logic, absent a *world (global) state* international law cannot meaningfully exist” (p. 3). Even with the evolution of ICs there is still no enforcement mechanism to hold leaders and governments of nation-states to include the United States, Russia, and China accountable for their rogue like behavior. She claims that over time ICs have been given more jurisdictional power (i.e. reviewing administration decisions, assessing state compliance with international law, etc.). According to Alter (2013) “there are at least twenty-four permanent international courts” (p. 4) currently in existence. Permanent international courts are today standalone judicial bodies created by nation states through a treaty, which are permanent fixtures within the international community; with permanent judges having jurisdiction to settle disputes or crimes under international law. Likewise, Alter (2013), views ICs as, “new political actors on the domestic and international stage. Their *international* nature allows ICs to circumvent domestical legal and political barriers and to create legal change across borders” (p. 4-5). Alter (2013), duly sees, “Law as the source of the ICs power and it is what broadens and unites stakeholders” (p. 5). Alter (2013) gives examples of ICs current abilities to wield power through law. “ICs have the power to issue binding rulings in the cases that are raised. Like their domestic counterparts, international judges issue rulings pertaining to the authority and legality of government

actions even though they have *no way to force governments to comply with their rulings*” (p. 8).

With the focus of this paper on Nation State accountability and their rogue-like behavior, time will tell whether such mechanisms and international institutions mentioned in this section will be able to collaborate with corporations, governments, legislators, and other stakeholders to develop more innovative concepts, procedures, and policies to be able to reign in the Superpower Rogue Nation State leaders and their associates alongside such leaders as former Rwandan Prime Minister Jean Kambanda.

Research Design

This master thesis examines the transformation of superpower nation-states such as the United States; which have gone from believing and supporting international law, global trade, multilateralism, relative peace and economic stability in exchange for the undoing of the principles of international law, seeking trade agreements on a *quid pro quo* basis, unilateralism, chaos, and economic instability in the world. The literature review closely assesses peer-reviewed research to reveal systemic concerns within the international bodies which fail to hold Superpowers unaccountable for their rogue-like behavior.

Peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed journals were sourced from Google Scholar. Strategic keywords were applied to refine the results for the database and search engine used. English was the preferred language during the search of relevant research articles published within the last 27 years, from 1999 to 2026. The term ‘Rogue Nation State’ was introduced as the database filter, and this term yielded numerous results. During the initial search the database filter term yielded 192,000 results. When the search was refined by dates (1999 – 2026) the search yielded 29,000 results. Peer-reviewed searches resulted in 6,680, and lastly a further research refinement (rogue + nation state accountability + united states + Russia +

China) resulted in 711 results. From the 711 results 32 articles were selected. These 32 articles were further reduced to 29 based on relevance with topics related to sovereignty, global trade, and international law. These 29 articles focus on the rogue behavior of Superpower countries and the limitations of international law. Moreover, the review articles contributed to the academic and global discourse of the behavior of rogue countries and the difficulties of holding superpower countries accountable. In conclusion, refined and evidence base criteria lead to a systematic review of included articles.

Case Selection

Boggs (2010) offers up examples of the U.S. violating and/or circumventing protocols and/or treaties. The behavior of the U.S. goes back a hundred years or more but let us start 78 years ago:

- Violated the Geneva Protocols (1948) regarding laws of occupation (in Iraq) that pertain to the disposition of property and the altering of domestic institutions.
- Violated several international conventions by carrying out wanton attacks on civilian populations, including in Japan, Korea, Indochina, Panama, Yugoslavia, and Iraq.
- Blocked global efforts to strengthen the 1967 Outer Space Treaty that would ban all weapons from space, while opposing U.N. resolutions urging strictly peaceful use of outer space.
- Violated the 1968 Nuclear Non-Proliferation Treaty that calls on the nuclear powers to move toward dismantling arsenals, forbids development of new weaponry, and requires a universal system of monitoring strongly opposed by Washington.
- Refused to endorse the International Criminal Court (ICC), insisting on special exemptions for its own government and military personnel.

- Refused to sign the Kyoto Protocol designed to fight global warming, insisting that any restrictions on its own industrial growth will harm its national economy and security interests.

These are merely some examples of the ways in which the United States disregards treaties and protocols. The U.S., when looked at closely has a clear pattern of belief in American exceptionalism. This exceptionalism is tied to Americas past by way of the ‘Discovery Doctrine’ which is tied very closely to the concept of Manifest Destiny. The Discovery Doctrine is a 15th century legal and historical principle that justified European claims to non-Christian lands and the subjugation of indigenous peoples, later codified in U.S. law. Similarly, the concept of Manifest Destiny was a 19th century doctrine and/or belief that the expansion of the United States throughout the North American continent was justified and inevitable. Now as then these doctrines or beliefs are deeply steeped in an ethnocentric view of U.S. culture, government and country as being superior to all others.

Results and Analysis

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These are merely some examples of the ways in which that the United States disregards treaties and protocols. The U.S., when looked at closely has a clear pattern of belief in American exceptionalism. This exceptionalism is tied to Americas past by the ‘Discovery Doctrine’ which is tied very closely to the concept of Manifest Destiny. The Discovery Doctrine is a 15th century legal and historical principle that justified European claims to non-Christian lands and the subjugation of indigenous peoples, later codified in U.S. law. Similarly, the concept of Manifest Destiny was a 19th century doctrine or belief that the expansion of the United States throughout the American continent was justified and inevitable. Now as then these doctrines or beliefs are deeply steeped in an ethnocentric view of U.S. culture, government and country as being superior to all others. This same superiority in conjunction with military might, nuclear weapons, and being on the UN Security Council with veto powers gives China, Russia, and the United States the idea that they are above international law. Boggs (2010) offers in his article, *The Crimes of Empire: Rogue Superpower and world Domination*. The Nuremberg trials prosecuted and convicted both Germans and Japanese of “crimes against peace” (p. 26) which involves the planning, initiation, and/or execution of aggressive war and was considered a serious violation of international law. While “crimes against peace” were considered a serious violation of

international law during the Nuremberg trials; in the 21st century the world barely blinks an eye regarding such a violation. America invades Venezuela, America and Israel start a conflict with Iran, Israel wages war with Palestine/Lebanon, and Russia wages war against Ukraine. There is a pattern; Nation State Aggressors Wage War and conflict with other nation states then the wars and conflict subside only to later start again. This back and forth has a missing element; accountability, prosecution, and conviction of aggressor nation states to include the United States, Russia, and China.

In the early 21st century such fiascos as the War in Iraq revealed Americas readiness to violate the U.N. Charter and revealing the willingness of the U.S. government to move forward with its imperialistic agenda. Boggs (2010) reveals other rejectionist examples by the U.S. towards the U.N. these examples came in 1979, 80, 81, 82, 83, and 84. December 1979 the U.S. along with France and Britain were in opposition to a resolution to negotiate to decrease the arms race; 12 months later the U.S. along with Britian rejected the halting of nuclear testing. In December of 1981 and 1983 the U.S. on its own disapproved an endorsement for the banning of chemical and biological warfare. With the U.S. conforming to the Outer Space Treaty in December of 1983, it was the only nation-state at the U.N. to oppose calls “for space to be used for strictly peaceful ends” (p. 156). There are many ardent examples of opposition to U.N. proposals and resolutions by the U.S. government, but it is not just the government but the very leadership of the United States who berates and minimizes the United Nations. During the lead-up to Washington making a military move in Iraq, then President George W. Bush warned the U.N. Security Council that their refusal to support American action would condemn the U.N. to irrelevance. During Donald J. Trump’s first term in office his remarks framed the U.N. as an institution with great potential but failing to meet that potential. The U.N. was too slow, too, bureaucratic, too focused on statements rather than action. Lastly Mr. Trump had remarked that the U.N. was too aligned

with global initiatives which he opposed. The U.N. is not the only international institution Donald J. Trump and past U.S. Presidents, and their administrations have shown contempt for. The International Criminal Court (ICC) is another institution in which Washington's concern with being able to have *'immunity from prosecutions* on the international stage could have a debilitating effect on the pursuit for international justice. Boggs (2010) expresses the concern that, "The leading superpower (U.S.) insisted on the absolute freedom to behave as it chooses" (p. 162). The words may never be spoken but if a nation state is demonstrating 'rogue-like' behavior in direct violation of international law then a 'rogue state' is what it is. Rogue states have in the past been defined as an authoritarian leaning regime that threatened other countries, waged reckless wars, and acted outside established international norms and systems. In the 21st century it is defined as a nation that is perceived as threatening global stability and often has the following characteristics: Authoritarian governance, support for terrorism, hostility towards other nation states, and defiance of international norms. As the U.S. has often shown disregard for international laws and diplomatic norms so too has Russia and China. Both, Russia and China are not publicly as well documented as the U.S., but some recent examples have been documented.

We must remember that what is being reported via the news media, and the governments of China, Russia, and the U.S. are only a fraction of the unseen pressures which these countries have and are applying to international institutions and the international community. The International Criminal Court (ICC) is an independent judicial institution dedicated to investigation, and prosecution of war crimes, crimes against humanity, genocide, and the crime of aggression. This institution has once again been targeted by the U.S. presidential administration. As early as 2018 National Security Advisor John Bolton under the first Trump administration announced, the U.S. would not cooperate with the ICC and threatened to retaliate against ICC staff and member countries that chose to investigate the

U.S. or its allies. Later that same year Donald J. Trump (2018) in his speech to the 73rd session of the United Nations General Assembly in New York City was quoted as saying, “The United States will provide no support in recognition to the International Criminal Court (ICC). As far as America is concerned, the ICC has no jurisdiction, no legitimacy, and no authority” (p. 7).

Kassam (2026) reports on two ICC judges who have been sanctioned by the Trump administration, the honorable judges Kimberly Prost and Luz del Carmen Ibanez Carranza. The imposed sanctions brought against both women have found the judges on terrorists watch list. Their personal lives upended by U.S. pressure in the form of personal credit cards, Amazon and Google accounts terminated not only for them but for their family members as well. This was brought on by Donald J. Trump in a 2025 executive order. Kassam (2026) writes, “Trump accused the court of engaging in “illegitimate and baseless actions targeting America and our close ally Israel.”” The U.S., and Israel along with 5 other countries are not signatories nor voted for the *Rome Statute*. The *Rome Statute* is a treaty which established the ICC in 1998 was signed by President Bill Clinton in 2000 but was never submitted to Congress for ratification. President George W. Bush unsigned the treaty in 2002 notifying the ICC and the U.N. secretary-general that the U.S. no longer intended to ratify nor did the U.S. have any commitment toward the ICC. To reiterate the United States has a long list of what the international community would say are ‘violations against the international community and humanity.’ It beckons one to think, even back in 1648 with the birth of sovereign states, that lack of accountability and enforcement may have been part of the policy planning for the wealthier and more powerful nation-states.

The continuous global media reporting of the U.S. governments rogue-like behavior is not just limited to America. Both Russia and China have done their share to sow death, destruction and chaos into the global community.

To understand the War in Ukraine provoked by President Vladimir Putin you need to understand the Russian Presidents' view of the former Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR). His view of *Ruski mir* (Russian World) and his view of 'compatriots abroad' is steeped in his modern belief system about the post-Soviet Union. During his 2018 address to the 6th World Congress of Compatriots Living Abroad, President Putin (2018), attempted to frame the downfall and defections from of the Soviet Union as a unique global community: "all of you together represent the tight-knit community of Russian compatriots and the huge united *Russian world*, which was never based exclusively on *ethnic, national, or religious principles*. It has brought together and united all those who are connected to Russia *spiritually*, who feel a *spiritual* link to our homeland, and who consider themselves to be Russian speakers and the carriers of Russian *culture* and history" (p. 1 para 3). The Russian world in which he speaks of is not representative of *formal citizenship* or *borders*; but, by *cultural* and *spiritual* association. Putin does not see former Soviet Republics as sovereign nation-states, but as Russian citizens with a cultural and spiritual association going about their business in the world all the while still being seen as under the rule of the Russian Federation. Ukraine is not a member of the North Atlantic Organization Treaty (NATO), nor a member of the European Union (EU). Ukraine has found itself a prime target for President Putin to begin his take back of regional sovereign nation-states which he sees as culturally and spiritually as part of the Russian world. Putin began his focus on Ukraine in 2013 culminating in Russia's illegal seizure of the Crimean Peninsula in March 2014. This violation of international law led the way to Putin's invasion of Ukraine in 2022. His war against Ukraine wages on, now in its fourth year threatening post-Soviet sovereign nation-states and the EU with war and domination.

China, unlike the United States and the Russian Federation have not yet shown outward physical aggression toward other nation-states. China may not meet the current

definition of a rouge state but does endeavor to engage in destabilizing and revisionist actions. China has demonstrated a continuous effort toward military build-up and coercion in the Indo Pacific. China has consistently conducted military exercises in and around the waters of Taiwan. China is quietly going about reshaping international order in ways that favor China's political and economic dominance. This is in stark contrast to America and Russia, but China should not be underestimated, with a large military presence and nuclear weapons; if China decided to use military force to reshape the Indo Pacific region, they would be a formidable force. Another tactic of reshaping international order that the global community must be mindful of is that the three superpower nation-states are likely working together to reshape future international order within the global community as they envision it to be.

With international laws, and treaties being violated by America and Russia, with China moving in the background the question turns to: What are the options for strengthening accountability by the international community?

Discussion and Conclusion / Policy Recommendations

Some stakeholders would say that there is no standing body of international law enforcement in the world, nor a strong willingness for such an institution. Current enforcement of international law comes in the form of toothless eloquent words of the United Nations Charter as in Chapter VII. In which the Security Council made up of the five permanent members (United State, Russia, China, United Kingdom, and France with 2 non-members sitting on the council at any given time). These members are authorized to determine the existence of threats to peace, a breach of peace, or act of aggression. The Security Council also has the power to impose mandatory sanctions to try to rectify violators of international law through different forms of sanctions. These may be economic sanctions (i.e. trade embargos against a country threatening peace), or diplomatic sanctions (cutting

diplomatic relations with said country), or using the military (i.e. using armed forces to maintain or restore international peace and security). Most embargoes are government-imposed restrictions on trade or other interactions designed to influence the behavior or policies of a targeted countries without using military force. As for Trade sanctions they involve restrictions on trade, financial transactions, or economic resources to coerce a government or entity into changing specific behavior (i.e. tariffs, export controls, freezing assets). Diplomatic sanctions come in the form of nonviolent measures that may involve the reduction or severance of diplomatic relations, (i.e. withdrawal of ambassadors or limiting diplomatic interactions). These sanctions can and do have the desired effects on smaller, economically unstable nation-states but with Superpower nation-states these forms of sanctions are much less effective in changing their specific behaviors. The tooth less eloquent words the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights Michell Bachelet were spoken in New York City in June of 2022 during open debate on the subject of, “Strengthening accountability and justice for serious violations of international law”. The High Commissioner states during the Open Debate that the United Nations in conjunction with the International Court of Justice (ICJ), the International Criminal Court (ICC), and other UN inter-governmental organizations, “have taken significant steps to advance accountability, often with a specific focus on fostering individual criminal responsibility for international crimes...and through further action of the Human Rights Council, there are currently no fewer than twelve specific human rights mechanisms active, addressing various forms of accountability.” High Commissioner Bachelet failed to mention any of ‘the no fewer than twelve specific human rights mechanisms currently active’. Bachelet writes, the UN Human Rights Council (UNHRC) has taken increasing steps in response to serious human rights violations which include creating mechanisms with “mandates to establish facts and the circumstances of violations, to collect, consolidate, preserve and analyze information and

evidence, to identify those responsible, and to make recommendations towards future accountability". She writes, "My office is continually strengthening its support to such mandates, which we see as key contributors to justice and rule of law". While High Commissioner Bachelet thinks identifying those responsible and making recommendations towards future accountability contributes to justice and the rule of law there are nation states in the world who have other plans and flaunt their contempt for international justice and the rule of law. While she was given this speech to the UN Security Council High-Level Open Debate members in 2022 the Russian Federation invaded Ukraine. Three years and three months later Donald J. Trump invades Venezuela, kidnaps the Venezuelan President and his wife. Six months after this incident Donald J. Trump in conjunction with Israel started an unprovoked war with Iran. Superpower rogue nation states don't care about international justice, the rules of law, international treaties, policies or non-government international agencies. Furthermore, there are some who admit that their actions and the power of the pen have no power to enforce. Ridley (2012) in her piece *Bush Convicted of War Crimes in Absentia*, reported that even though the Kuala Lumpur Crimes Commission found President Bush, Vice-President Cheney, Secretary of Defense Rumsfeld along with their key legal advisors guilty of war crimes the commission admits, that its verdict is merely declaratory in nature. "The tribunal has no power of enforcement, no power to impose any custodial sentence on anyone". Within the context of the ICC, this institution has not had any tribunals of any past Presidents nor their administrative staff personnel since it began operations in July 2002. The ICC also does not hold criminal tribunals in Absentia. Again, with the ICC requiring that the person on trial for war crimes be present in their courts allows alleged Superpower war criminals a get-out of jail free pass; because no one will step up to transport and present these particular people to the ICC for trial. Using the concept of absentia as a reason not to hold alleged war criminal(s) accountable is a policy failing of the ICC but also

makes a statement about the nation-states in question and their willingness to not hold their leaders accountable for alleged war crimes as well. With the ineffectiveness of sanctions, and the viable but tooth-less procedures and policies of non-governmental institutions, there are still opportunities available to bring about accountability.

There are some key, fundamental elements which have been, are now, and will have to be considered in the future. Firstly, having the will to do what is necessary for the good of Humanity first and foremost over the will of countries' governments which do not always have their citizens' best interests at heart. It means bringing creativity, and critical thinking along with grit to be prepared to make hard choices that will come with reshaping our countries and governments from individual countries and governments into a global governing body for Humanity. Secondly, funding. The 20th century and the first quarter of the 21st century have shown how Governments use defunding and withdrawal of their countries' funds to manipulate the Charters, policies, and procedures of non-governmental institutions. Here to creativity, critical thinking, grit, and the understanding that there will be hard work, tough decisions, and severed relations during the process of moving the needle of positivity toward better global stability, with international cooperation, respect, and adherence to international laws by all parties and governments, culminating in a world society which puts all of Humanity first no matter what the topic of discussions are or will be. Several authors have arrived at similar points in their papers. According to Adissa and Adham (2025), "Beyond tools, what is needed is a reconfiguration of the architecture of global cooperation itself. New coalitions must be built that transcend the Westphalian model of state-only diplomacy...The global community must reimagine diplomacy as an anticipatory and collaborative process, rather than merely a reactive one" (p. 156). Author Vesselin Popovski (2022) stated:

The new security challenges urge finding new methods to address them, as traditional conflict prevention and management models might be ill suited. The risks to peace and security have become abundant with protracted conflicts, transnational terrorist and criminal networks, rapid sophistication of weapons, significant number of displaced people, and overall high level of violence outside armed conflict. Further challenges come from new technologies placing the capacity to disrupt global stability in the hands of very few and invisible actors (p. 5).

Although the work before nation states and humanity will be hard, the very institutions for advancement in international cooperation, collaboration, and multilateralism had been formed during the early 20th century. The UN, ICC, ICJ and many other non-governmental institutions are brick-and-mortar institutions which adhere to cooperation, collaboration, and multilateralism. But their procedures and policies have not kept up with the fast-paced events in the global arena. Transformative changes are long overdue. Adham et al. (2025) eloquently states; “As the mechanisms of war evolve, so too must the systems of peacekeeping” (p. 157). In the last decade scholars have addressed changes and upgrades within the above institutions. Some authors have suggested modifications to institutional legal frameworks, others recommend doing away with what is known as the ‘P5 veto’ within the UN.

Many of the United Nations (UN) 193 members have come to recognize the ‘P5 veto’ as an obstacle to inclusive and collaborative decision-making within the UN. According to Popovski (2022), “The abuse of the veto damages the whole UN system” (p. 10). History shows that there was discontent with the veto power of the P5 (China, France, Russian Federation, United Kingdom, and the United States) as early as 1945 by many of the founding members, such as Australia, Poland, and many Latin American countries just to mention a few. They saw the veto power as a temporary mechanism to be tested over the first

10 years of the UN's operation. Article 109 was drafted with the belief of casting aside the veto during the review conference in 1955. In Popovski's article (2022), Re-imagining the United Nations Organization in which he comes up with four imaginary scenarios for a future UN. Of the four, the fourth scenario is by far the most viable scenario. He envisions the creation of a new UN organization with a new Charter like the 1945 Charter. The new UN would assume everything which works well within the current system, restore the Security Council along with implementation of proposals from Secretary-General Antonio Guterres's "Our Common Agenda Report (OCA)" (p. 4). Including, the drafting of "periodic Charter review mechanisms, the securing of genuine international rules of law, and so forth. Popovski concludes, that if a certain number of member states were to come together and create a new UN organization with the veto mechanism unavailable to any of the members, there would be nothing Russia, China, and now the United States could do about it. These three countries could decide to join or not join the new UN organization or decide to start their own organization as Donald Trump has done with the creation of the 'Board of Peace' on January 22, 2026. Popovski (2022), "What is crystal clear is that international peace and security is too important to be left entirely to the current Security Council" (p.10).

Author, Adham et al. (2025) wrote, regarding international law in the hope of avoiding a future of constant conflicts; traditional governance structures are no longer adequate. The belief is that there needs to be an expanding and modernizing of the "international legal framework". Furthermore, they see "existing laws of war and humanitarian codes" wholly inadequate for issues such as "cyber espionage, autonomous weapon use, or algorithmic manipulation of civilian populations" (p. 156).

Although the UN serves as the cornerstone of the international legal system, the International Criminal Court (ICC) and the International Court of Justice (ICJ) have a large role to play in the upgrading and reforming of the 'international legal framework' under

which these institutions currently operate. Many experts and scholars have agreed over time that amending the UN Charter to limit and or do away with the veto powers of the P5 would be a great move toward promoting the rule of law. Another recommended reform is the mandatory reporting and follow-up which would improve transparency and accountability for those nation states unwilling to comply with the ICC and ICJ. Nation states which believe in multilateralism, the rule of law, and a democratic way of life should show resolve in the implementation of ICC and ICJ decisions beyond the UNSC in the hope of reducing reliance on the P5 regarding enforcement actions. In 2024, Ali, Hassan, and Mousa expressed recognition that Civil Society Organizations(CSOs), and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's) have played an ever-increasing role in global governance and should be brought to the big table in order to help nation states to “promote awareness of international law, advocate for its implementation, and hold states and other actors accountable for their actions” (p. 4). Some of the NGOs on the front-line of promoting awareness, monitoring, documenting, and advocating for justice and accountability are the Human Rights Watch, Amnesty International, and the International Commission of Jurists. Amnesty International in 1998 had written about how world governments came together during that year to formulate and adopt what would be “The International Criminal Court - *16 Fundamental Principles for just, fair, and effective international criminal court*” (p. 1). These fundamental principles are quite profound and warrant being reiterated within this paper:

1. *The Court should have jurisdiction over the crime of genocide.*
2. *The court should have jurisdiction over other crimes against humanity.*
3. *The court should have jurisdiction over serious violations of humanitarian law in international and non-international armed conflict.*
4. *The court must ensure justice for women.*
5. *The court must have inherent (automatic) jurisdiction.*

6. *The court must have the same universal jurisdiction over these crimes as any of its state's parties.*
7. *The court must have the power in all cases to determine whether it has jurisdiction and whether to exercise it without political interference from any source.*
8. *The court should be an effective complement to national courts when these courts are unable or unwilling to bring to justice those responsible for these grave crimes.*
9. *An independent prosecutor should have the power to initiate investigation on his or her own initiative, based on information from any source, subject only to appropriate judicial scrutiny, and present search and arrest warrants and indictments to the court for approval.*
10. *No political body, including the Security Council, or states, should have the power to stop or even delay an investigation or prosecution under any circumstances whatsoever.*
11. *To ensure that justice is done, the court must develop effective victim and witness protection programs, involving the assistance of all state's parties, without prejudicing the rights of suspect and the accused.*
12. *The court must have the power to award victims and their families' reparations, including restitution, compensation and rehabilitation.*
13. *The statute must ensure suspects and accused, the right to a fair trial in accordance with the highest international standards at all stages of the proceedings.*
14. *All states parties, including their courts and officials; must provide full cooperation without delay to the court at all stages of the proceedings.*

15. The court should be financed by the regular UN budget, supplemented, under appropriate safeguards for its independence, by the peace-keeping budget and by a voluntary trust fund.

16. There should be no reservations to the statute.

After 28 years most of the 16 fundamental principles have been adopted by many world governments. But unfortunately, principles 14, 15, and 16 have failed to be incorporated with eagerness and effectiveness. The United States, Russian Federation, and China consistently fail to give their full cooperation to the ICC. International courts continue to be affected by state sponsored financing via the UN's budget, which can call into question judicial independence of the courts. As well as most sovereign nation states are not will give up any amount of sovereignty or their 'National Security'.

Another challenge within the UN, ICC, and ICJ other than the P5 veto is the enforcement of judgements by these institutions. The ICC and the ICJ in their lack of having direct enforcement mechanisms to hold nation states such as the United States, Russia Federation, and China accountable due to their political power, sovereignty, immunity, military might, etc. ensures the undermining of the effectiveness of these organizations.

We know and understand that the mechanisms to advance International Law, and the current institutions which uphold international laws are already in place. The lack of will by remaining democracies, and the rise of autocracy, dictatorships, and the changing roles of countries such as the United States have put the future of the global community in a constant state of chaos and uncertainty. When Astronauts go to space and look back at earth, they do not see the lines that our maps have drawn on them to identify different countries; they see one planet, one race, the human race. Global state governance, a global state community, and a United Global State Federation (UGSF) institution managed by a comprehensive global

state legal system is the direction humanity is going in. The will must be found and the acceptance that hard work is and will be needed to begin the transformation which is required to move humanity toward a future of more peace, stability, and economic prosperity. At this time in human history, the needs of the many outweigh the needs of the few and all that is needed for the triumph of the few is for the many to do nothing. Let's begin!

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